

GW Vir instability strip in the light of new observations of PG 1159 stars

Paulina Sowicka

Nicolaus Copernicus Astronomical Center, Polish Academy of Sciences, ul. Bartycka 18, PL-00-716, Warszawa, Poland

White dwarfs, stars at the latest stages of evolution of low- to intermediate-mass stars, show a diversity of pulsation properties. There are three classical groups of white dwarf pulsators along the white dwarf cooling track: H-deficient GW Vir pre-white dwarf stars, He-rich DBVs, and H-rich DAVs [see e.g., 1]. GW Vir stars lie in the first instability strip entered by a post-asymptotic giant branch (AGB) star. White dwarf stars residing in the GW Vir domain span a large range of effective temperatures (≈ 75 -250 kK) and surface gravities ($\log g \approx 5.5$ -8). Most GW Vir pulsators are of the PG 1159 spectral type but there are also [WC]-types (central stars of planetary nebulae with Wolf-Rayet spectra of carbon sequence). The main spectral feature of the PG 1159 class is the absorption trough made up by the He II $\lambda 4686 \text{ \AA}$ and adjacent C IV lines. PG 1159 stars exhibit He-, C-, and O-rich surface abundances with strong variations of the He/C/O ratio from star to star and, in some cases, traces of heavier elements.

Some stars show photometrically detectable low-amplitude, multiperiodic pulsations with periods as short as a few minutes, that are due to nonradial gravity modes driven by the κ mechanism associated with the partial ionization of the K-shell electrons of carbon and/or oxygen in the envelope [2, 3]. A theoretically predicted ϵ mechanism, that is connected with the changes in the nuclear energy generation rate in the stars with He burning shells, was also proposed as an additional mechanism responsible for the highest frequency modes. In theoretical calculations both mechanisms form overlapping regions in the H-R diagram but despite a number of stars lying in this region, the ϵ mechanism has still not been observed to operate in any star [4].

PG 1159 stars are thought to be formed as a result of a “born-again” episode - a very late thermal pulse (VLTP) experienced by a hot white dwarf during its early cooling phase or a late thermal pulse (LTP) that occurs during the post-AGB evolution when H-burning is still active [e.g., 5]. This evolutionary history is reflected in their chemical abundances; especially elements like H and N are imprints of the prior evolution as they are tracers of when the progenitor experienced the final thermal pulse. That makes these stars important to study from the evolutionary point of view, as they are supposed to be the main progenitors of H-deficient white dwarf stars.

The impurity of GW Vir instability strip

The striking difference between the GW Vir instability strip and the domains of DBVs and DAVs is that the GW Vir one is not pure, i.e. not all stars in that section of the H-R diagram show pulsations, in contrast to the two others. Thus their interiors that can be studied using aster-

oseismology do not necessarily represent the interiors of all PG 1159 stars. According to the literature, only about 50% of them pulsate [6]. Why is that the case? What separates the pulsators from the nonpulsators?

The role of nitrogen

The existence of both pulsating and nonpulsating stars within the GW Vir instability strip was a real challenge to pulsation theory. Firstly, a nitrogen dichotomy was observed, meaning that all N-rich (about 1% in mass) stars are pulsators, whereas N-poor (below 0.01% in mass) stars are all nonpulsators. Therefore the hypothesis was put forward that nitrogen, despite its rather small abundance even in N-rich stars, is essential for pulsation driving [7]. On the other hand, [8] argued that predominantly a high oxygen abundance is responsible for that. The whole picture is complicated by the variety of surface abundances in PG 1159 stars (basically each star has its own unique composition), the role of metallicity, and the admixture of helium “poisoning” the development of pulsations [6]. That was until the calculations showed that only the stars with the most oxygen and carbon (depending on their configuration) can pulsate, and a pulsator and nonpulsator with the same carbon and oxygen abundance, but different amount of nitrogen, were studied, confirming the first findings [9].

The final piece to the puzzle

The part played by nitrogen as a tracer of the previous evolutionary history is therefore interesting in this context. Is N essential for pulsation driving? Are there surface patterns that are indicative of driving? Is a VLTP a necessity for destabilizing a star to develop pulsations? If yes, this would allow the important conclusion that the GW Vir stars have a fundamentally different evolutionary history than the non-pulsators. However, the only culprit in this view of the excitation theory and abundance patterns of these stars remained - PG 1144+005, the only known N-rich PG 1159 star that was not previously shown to pulsate.

A number of authors observed PG 1144+005 in search for the elusive pulsations. Starting with the pioneering work of Grauer and collaborators in the 1980’s, through more recent and extensive studies by Schuh and Steiner and collaborators, none of their efforts bore fruit. Only the latter [10] provided observational data and detection threshold. Their data showed a light curve with no visible variability and a semi-amplitude of about 0.02 mag. The lack of variability was then reflected in the Fourier amplitude spectrum, where no peak exceeded an amplitude of 4 mmag. We revisited the object and observed it in 2018 with the 10-m GTC telescope to de-

tect photometric variability in 1.1 hr of observations with a semi-amplitude of about 5 mmag and preliminary pulsation frequencies in the range $\approx 80\text{--}120$ [d⁻¹]. This was confirmed in 2021 with a follow-up observing run with the 1-m Lesedi telescope. Fourier amplitude spectra of five nights of observations showed four main groups of pulsation modes with varying amplitudes over the course of the observing run. Highly variable amplitudes and/or frequencies, and even a complete disappearance of the pulsations for a period of time are often observed in GW Vir stars. The detected frequencies were consistent with g-mode pulsations excited by the κ mechanism operating in PG 1159 stars. [11].

This provided the final piece of evidence that there is a clear separation, namely all known N-rich PG 1159 stars pulsate and the N-poor ones do not. The important conclusion follows: the pulsating and non-pulsating PG 1159 stars have different evolutionary history, and it seems necessary that a star undergoes a VLTP to develop pulsations, while nitrogen is a tracer of this evolutionary history. Does it mean that the picture is now complete? Or will we find more N-rich nonpulsators and N-poor pulsators if we push the detection limit down to further challenge the current theory?

The search for more

Even though the evolutionary link to the nitrogen abundance appears to hold, it is based on a small sample of objects for which we have full information. Out of 58 known PG 1159 stars, only 15 have their nitrogen abundance assessed, still statistically a small number considering the total number of known PG 1159 stars. A detailed assessment of elemental abundances for a large sample of these stars is therefore highly demanded.

Because the information about variability is available for only a handful of PG 1159 stars, we carry out a survey for variability with a set of telescopes of different sizes ranging from 1-m to 10-m, to cover both the brightest and faintest targets with good temporal resolution in at least 1-hr long observing blocks (Sowicka et al. 2022, in prep.). The goal is to discover new pulsators, especially among those not checked for variability, and re-observe known nonpulsating PG 1159 stars to improve the previous detection limits for non-variability. Figure 1 shows exemplary 30 amplitude spectra from the survey. What is evident even among this sample is that the majority of those stars don't show variability even with a lower detection threshold. The true pulsator occurrence in the GW Vir instability strip might therefore be lower than the previously reported 50%.

Take away points

Pulsators and nonpulsators can be found within the

boundaries of GW Vir instability strip - the true fraction might be even lower than previously reported 50%. This discrepancy has been explained by different evolutionary histories of pre-white dwarf progenitors in the AGB phase, then reflected in the surface abundance with nitrogen and hydrogen being the trace elements. With the discovery of pulsations in the only remaining N-rich PG 1159 star, PG 1144+005, we provided the last missing piece to the current theory. We also proved that it is worth re-observing known non-pulsating PG 1159 stars with better detection thresholds together with those never photometrically checked. For a complete picture spectroscopic observations aiming at deriving surface abundances of all crucial elements including nitrogen are needed. Our ultimate goal is to obtain the first statistically significant sample of well-studied PG 1159 stars with information on their evolutionary history and excitation of pulsations.

Figure 1: Exemplary amplitude spectra from our survey for variability in PG 1159 stars. One previously known pulsator (middle row 2nd from the left), PG 1144+005 (bottom row 1st from the left), and a candidate that still needs confirmation (2nd row from the bottom, 4th from the left).

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Short CV

2008–2012: BSc in Astronomy, Jagiellonian University, Cracow, Poland
 2012–2014: MSc in Astronomy, Jagiellonian University, Cracow, Poland
 2015–2016: Student Support Astronomer, ING, La Palma, Spain
 2014–present: PhD in Astronomy, NCAC of the PAS, Warsaw, Poland